

Polycyclic Systems. Part XI. A Synthesis of 4'-(1,2-Dimethylpropyl)-6'-methylindeno-(2',3'-1,2)phenanthrene

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The synthesis of 4'-(1,2-dimethylpropyl)-6'-methylindeno-(2',3'-1,2)phenanthrene, a supposed dehydrogenation product of ergosterol, is described. The synthetic hydrocarbon is found to be different from that derived from ergosterol. This and a similar observation regarding the dehydrogenation product of cholesterol, published earlier¹, clearly show the inadequacy of Bergmann's mechanism of the formation of indenophenanthrene derivatives from the steroids.

The selenium dehydrogenation of the steroids usually leads to a complicated mixture of higher aromatic hydrocarbons^{2,4}, of which a minor fraction has been shown to consist of indeno-(2',3'-1,2)phenanthrene derivatives. In the previous part¹ various mechanisms⁵⁻⁹ of formation of these hydrocarbons from the steroids (I) have been discussed and a synthesis of 4'-isobutyl-6'-methylindeno-(2',3'-1,2)-phenanthrene(II), the expected dehydrogenation product of cholesterol (I: R=H), according to Bergmann's mechanism¹ has been described. The synthesis of its higher homologue (III), which was undertaken simultaneously, has now been accomplished, following the general method of Nasipuri and Roy¹⁰. The results clearly show that this hydrocarbon (III) is also different from that derived from ergosterol⁹ (I:R=Me, with two additional double bonds). Bergmann's mechanism⁹ of the formation of indenophenanthrene derivatives from the steroids is thus seemingly untenable and the structures of these hydrocarbons need revision.

- Nasipuri, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1961, 4230.
- Diels *et al.*, *Annalen*, 1927, 459, 1; Diels, *Ber.*, 1933, 66, 487, 1122.
- Diels and Karstens, *Annalen*, 1930, 478, 129; Ruzicka *et al.*, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1933, 16, 812; Diels and Stephan, *Annalen*, 1937, 527, 279.
- Ruzicka and Goldberg, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1937, 20, 1245.
- Cook *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 1319; and also ref. 7.
- Rosenheim and King, *Chem. & Ind.*, 1933, 52, 299.
- Cook *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 1227.
- Cf. Bernal and Crowfoot, *ibid.*, 1935, 93.
- Bergmann, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1938, 60, 2306.
- Nasipuri and Roy, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1961, 3361.

Isopropyl methyl ketone was condensed with ethyl cyanoacetate under the Knoevenagel condition¹¹ and product (IV) hydrogenated to ethyl 2-cyano-3,4-dimethylpentanoate (V: R=CN). Alternatively, isobutyraldehyde and diethyl malonate were condensed together and the resultant diethyl isobutylidenemalonate (VI) was treated with methylmagnesium iodide¹² to furnish ethyl 2-ethoxycarbonyl-3,4-dimethylpentanoate (V: R=CO₂Et). Both the esters (V: R=CN and V: R=CO₂Et) were separately hydrolysed to 3,4-dimethylpentanoic acid (VII) (amide m.p. 140°), the acid chloride condensed with the sodio-derivative of ethyl α -methylacetoacetate¹³, and the product ammonolysed¹ to afford ethyl 2,5,6-trimethyl-3-oxoheptanoate (VIII) in quite good yield. The latter was hydrolysed to the corresponding β -keto-acid and then treated with piperidine hydrochloride and formaldehyde in acid medium according to the procedure of Mannich and Curtaz¹⁴. 1-*N*-Piperidino-2,5,6-trimethylheptan-3-one (IX: R=—NC₅H₁₀) was obtained in about 50% yield, the structure of the aminoketone being confirmed by its conversion into 4,7,8-trimethyl-5-oxononanoic acid (IX:R=CH₂CO₂H) and by an independent synthesis of the latter from the β -oxo-ester (VIII) by the usual procedure¹.

The requisite Mannich-base (IX:R=—NC₅H₁₀), thus made available, was converted into its methiodide and the latter condensed with the potassio-derivative of 4'-methoxycarbonyl-3'-oxocyclopenteno-(1',2')phenanthrene (XI: R=H), obtained directly

11. Cope *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1941, **63**, 3452.

12. Prout, *ibid.*, 1952, **74**, 5915; Prout *et al.*, *ibid.*, 1954, **76**, 1911.

13. Cardwell, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1949, 715.

14. Mannich and Curtaz, *Arch. Pharm.*, 1926, **264**, 741.

by the Dieckmann cyclisation of the di-ester¹⁰ (X) in presence of potassium in benzene. The gummy product (XI: R = -CH₂. CHMe. COCH₂CHMe. CHMe₂) was hydrolysed to the pentacyclic ketone (XII), m.p. 203°; the latter was reduced with lithium aluminium hydride and subsequently dehydrogenated with palladium-charcoal to 4'-(1,2-dimethylpropyl)-6'-methylindeno-(2',3'-1,2)phenanthrene (III), m.p. 195-96°. The hydrocarbon was characterised through the formation of a monoketone (orange), m.p. 196°, by chromic acid oxidation and a red trinitrofluorenone complex, m.p. 200-201°. The hydrocarbon from the dehydrogenation product of ergosterol³ and the ketonic derivatives thereof had m.p.s 215° and 175° respectively and are thus completely different from the present compounds.

The ultraviolet absorption spectra of the ketone (XII) and the hydrocarbon (III) along with some analogous compounds are shown in Fig. 1 and Fig. 2.

*EXPERIMENTAL

Ethyl 2-Cyano-3,4-dimethylpentanoate (V: R=CN).—A mixture of isopropyl methyl ketone (76 g.), ethyl cyanoacetate (100 g.), glacial acetic acid (42 ml), ammonium acetate (13.5 g.), and dry benzene (175 ml) was heated under reflux using a Dean-Stark water-separator till no more water separated (8-10 hrs.). The product was poured into cold water, the benzene layer separated, washed with NaHCO₃ solution, then with water, dried, and distilled. Ethyl α -cyano- β -isopropylcrotonate (IV) was obtained as a colorless oil (104 g.), b.p. 110-12°/10 mm. This was hydrogenated in presence of 10% Pd-C (500 mg.) in ethanol (300 ml), the absorption of one mole of hydrogen being completed in 2 hours. The product was filtered and distilled to furnish the ester (V: R=CN) (100 g.), b.p. 95°/5-7 mm. (Found: C, 65.0; H, 9.9. C₁₀H₁₇O₂N requires C, 65.5; H, 9.2%).

Ethyl 2-Ethoxycarbonyl-3,4-dimethylpentanoate (V: R=CO₂Et).—A solution of ethyl isobutylidenemalonate¹¹ (21.4 g.) in dry benzene (30 ml) was added to a Grignard reagent, prepared from magnesium (2.4 g.), methyl iodide (14.2 g.), and dry ether (45 ml). After the addition was complete, the reaction mixture was heated under reflux for 1 hour and then decomposed with ice and H₂SO₄ (dil.). The organic layer was separated and the aqueous phase once extracted with ether. The total organic layer was washed with water, dried (Na₂SO₄), solvent evaporated, and distilled. The ester (V: R=CO₂Et) was obtained as a colorless liquid (14.8 g.), b.p. 130-32°/9 mm. (Found: C, 62.1; H, 10.0. C₁₇H₂₂O₄ requires C, 62.6; H, 9.5%).

3,4-Dimethylpentanoic Acid (VII).—(a). A mixture of ethyl 2-cyano-3,4-dimethylpentanoate (V:R=CN) (42 g.), KOH (60 g.), and ethylene glycol (150 ml) was refluxed for 10 hours. Ethylene glycol was partly removed by distillation, the residue was diluted with water, and acidified. The liberated acid was taken up in ether, dried over Na₂SO₄,

*M.p.'s are corrected. The UV absorption spectra were determined on a Beckman spectrophotometer in ethanolic solution.

FIG. 1

FIG. 2

the solvent evaporated, and the residue distilled under atmospheric pressure to furnish the acid (22 g.), b.p. 220-30°/760mm. A good middle fraction was analysed. (Found: C, 64.2;

H, 10.8. $C_7H_{14}O_2$ requires C, 64.6; H, 10.7%). The *amide* was prepared in the usual way and crystallised from water in white flakes, m.p. 140°. (Found: C, 65.0; H, 11.8; N, 11.0. $C_7H_{13}ON$ requires C, 65.1; H, 11.6; N, 10.8%).

(b). Ethyl 2-ethoxycarbonyl-3,4-dimethylpentanoate (V: $R=CO_2Et$) (15 g.) was heated with ethanolic KOH (15 g. in 75 ml) for 8 hours. After evaporation of the ethanol, the aqueous solution was acidified and extracted thoroughly with ether. The residue after removal of the solvent was heated at 160-65° for 5 hours in an oil-bath and then distilled to provide 3,4-dimethylpentanoic acid (7 g.), b.p. 220-25°/760 mm. It was also characterised through the formation of the *amide*, m.p. 140°.

Ethyl 2,5,6-Trimethyl-3-oxoheptanoate (VIII).—A solution of 3,4-dimethylpentanoyl chloride (37 g.), b.p. 158°/760 mm, in dry ether (150 ml) was gradually introduced into an ice-cold slurry of sodio-derivative of ethyl α -methylacetoacetate, prepared from ethyl α -methylacetoacetate (36 g.), finely pulverised sodium (5.8 g.), and dry ether (350 ml) with stirring. The mixture was allowed to stand overnight, refluxed on the water bath for 1 hour, cooled, and decomposed with an excess of 3*N*- H_2SO_4 . The ethereal layer was separated, once washed with water, dried (Na_2SO_4), the solvent removed, and the residue distilled to afford the *ethyl 3,6,7-trimethyl-2,4-dioxo-octane-3-carboxylate* (28 g.), b.p. 125°/5 mm. (Found: C, 65.1; H, 9.8. $C_{14}H_{24}O_4$ requires C, 65.6; H, 9.4%).

The above ester (28 g.) in dry ether (50 ml) was cooled in a freezing mixture and a rapid stream of dry ammonia was passed into it for 1 hour. The mixture was decomposed with 3*N*-HCl (excess) with vigorous shaking and the organic matter thoroughly extracted with ether. The ethereal layer was once washed with water, dried (Na_2SO_4), and the solvent evaporated. The *ester* (VIII) was obtained as a colorless oil (14 g.), b.p. 100-105°/5 mm. (Found: C, 67.0; H, 10.4. $C_{12}H_{22}O_3$ requires C, 67.3; H, 10.2%).

1-*N-Piperidino-2,5,6-trimethylheptan-3-one* (IX: $R=-NC_5H_{10}$).—The preceding ester (VIII) (12.5 g.) was shaken with a solution of KOH (3.9 g.) in water (150 ml) at 0° for 48 hours. Some neutral matter separated at this stage which was removed in ether. To the cold aqueous solution piperidine hydrochloride (7.7 g.) was added and 40% formaldehyde solution (6.5 ml) gradually introduced, keeping the solution acidic to Methyl red by occasional addition of HCl (conc.). The mixture was stirred in the cold for 8 hours and then left overnight at 0°. After removal of the neutral matter with ether, the acidic solution was basified with strong aqueous KOH. The liberated *aminoketone* was extracted with ether, dried (K_2CO_3), and distilled. It was obtained as an oil (7 g.), b.p. 125°/8 mm. (Found: C, 75.0; H, 12.6. $C_{13}H_{20}ON$ requires C, 75.3; H, 12.1%).

4,7,8-*Trimethyl-5-oxononanoic Acid* (IX: $R=-CH_2CO_2H$).—(a). The ester (VIII) (2 g.) was heated with a solution of ethyl β -bromopropionate (2 g.) and pulverised potassium (0.4 g.) in dry benzene (10 ml) for 10 hours. The product was cooled, decomposed with acid-water, and the organic matter collected in ether. The residue after evaporation of the solvent was heated with HCl (conc., 10 ml) for 8 hours. The organic acid, thus obtained, was extracted with ether and finally distilled to furnish a viscous oil (0.5 g.), b.p. 190°/10 mm. It formed a *semicarbazone* which crystallised from methanol in white nodules, m.p. 128-30°. (Found: C, 57.2; H, 9.6; N, 15.4. $C_{15}H_{25}O_3N_3$ requires C, 57.5; H, 9.2; N, 15.5%).

(b). The above acid was also obtained by condensing diethyl malonate with the methiodide of the aminoketone (IX: R = $-\text{NC}_3\text{H}_{10}$) (*vide infra*) in presence of ethanolic sodium ethoxide⁷ and hydrolysing the product. It gave a semicarbazone, m.p. and mixed m.p. with the above sample, 128-30°.

5',6',7',7'a-Tetrahydro-4'-(1,2-dimethylpropyl)-6'-methyl-5-oxoindeno-(2',3'-1,2)phenanthrene (XII).—Methyl β -(2-methoxycarbonyl-1-phenanthryl)propionate¹⁰ (4.2 g.), finely divided potassium (0.6 g.), dry benzene (25 ml), and a drop of methanol were refluxed in the water-bath for 4 hours. Meanwhile, the aminoketone (IX: R = $-\text{NC}_3\text{H}_{10}$) (6.2 g.) was converted into the methiodide by treatment with methyl iodide (2 ml) in the usual way. The white crystalline methiodide, thus produced, was dissolved in absolute methanol (20 ml) and introduced into the cold mixture of the Dieckmann product. The whole was left overnight, refluxed for 1 hour, decomposed with cold H_2SO_4 (dil.) and extracted with benzene. The benzene extract after acidic and alkaline wash was dried and evaporated to leave a gummy residue which could not be induced to crystallise and was hydrolysed as follows.

The crude product (5 g.), left after removal of the low-boiling impurities up to b.p. 100°/0.8 mm was heated with HCl (conc., 60 ml), glacial acetic acid (120 ml), and water (6 ml) in an atmosphere of CO_2 . Crystals separated as hydrolysis proceeded. After 20 hours of reflux, the reaction mixture was cooled to room temperature and the separated crystalline solid collected by filtration, affording the crude ketone (3 g.), m.p. 188-90°. This was purified by chromatography over neutral alumina (150 g.), then by a few crystallisations from benzene-petroleum ether (b. p. 40-60°), and finally obtained in white prisms (1.5 g.), m.p. 203°. (Found: C, 87.9; H, 7.6. $\text{C}_{27}\text{H}_{26}\text{O}$ requires C, 88.0; H, 7.6%). λ_{max} (Fig. 1): 220, 250, 275, 287, 300, and 330 μ ($\log \epsilon$, 4.45, 4.15, 4.57, 4.57, 4.64, and 4.54 respectively); λ_{min} : 237, 255, 281, 293, and 309 μ ($\log \epsilon$, 4.03, 4.10, 4.53, 4.51, and 4.36 respectively).

4'-(1,2-Dimethylpropyl)-6'-methylindeno-(2',3'-1,2)phenanthrene (III: R = Me).—The above unsaturated ketone (1 g.) was reduced with LiAlH_4 (1.2 g.) in tetrahydrofuran (75 ml) by refluxing on a water-bath for 2 hours. The crude alcohol (1 g.), worked up in the usual way, was intimately mixed with 10% Pd-C (600 mg.) and heated at 310-320° for 2 hours in a metal bath. The melt was extracted with hot benzene, filtered, the solvent evaporated, and the residual solid crystallised from benzene-petroleum ether (b.p. 40-60°) to afford the hydrocarbon (III: R = Me) (500 mg.), m.p. 190°. This was further purified by sublimation at 280-300°/0.01 mm and crystallised thrice from benzene-petroleum ether in white plates, m.p. 196°. (Found: C, 92.5; H, 7.4. $\text{C}_{27}\text{H}_{26}$ requires C, 92.5; H, 7.4%). λ_{max} (Fig. 2): 220, 240, 274, 285, 301, 310, 323, 350, 358, and 367 μ ($\log \epsilon$, 4.6, 4.42, 4.76, 4.91, 4.60, 4.43, 4.42, 3.24, 2.86, and 3.24 respectively); λ_{min} : 238, 250, 277, 296, 308, 317, 345, 356, and 362 μ ($\log \epsilon$, 4.40, 4.17, 4.69, 4.56, 4.42, 4.30, 2.91, 2.83, and 2.67 respectively).

The hydrocarbon afforded a trinitrofluorenone complex in benzene-ethanol solution from which it crystallised in red nodules, m.p. 201°. (Found: N, 6.4. $\text{C}_{26}\text{H}_{24}\text{O}_7\text{N}_3$ requires N, 6.3%).

4'-(1,2-Dimethylpropyl)-6'-methyl-1-oxoindeno-(2',3'-1,2)phenanthrene. — The preceding hydrocarbon (30 mg.) was heated with sodium dichromate (100 mg.) in glacial

acetic acid (3 ml) for 15 minutes. The mixture was then diluted, the precipitate collected by filtration, the crude *ketone* once crystallised from ethyl acetate in orange needles (30 mg.), m.p. 192°. This was absorbed over alumina (5 g.) and the orange layer eluted by benzene. After evaporation of benzene, the orange solid was crystallised twice from ethyl acetate and finally from acetic acid to afford orange needles (7 mg.), m.p. 196°. (Found: C, 89.0; H, 6.6. $C_{17}H_{14}O$ requires C, 89.0; H, 6.6%). The ketone developed an intense violet colour in H_2SO_4 (conc.).

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